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Gender Inequality and Access to Maternal Healthcare Services in Rural Nigeria: Implications for Women's Health Outcomes

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ABSTRACT

This study examined gender inequality and access to maternal healthcare services in rural Nigeria and its implications for women's health outcomes. The paper aimed to assess how gender-based disparities, socio-economic barriers, and cultural beliefs shape women's access to quality maternal health services and to identify policy interventions for improving health equity. Grounded in the Health Belief Model (HBM), the study explored how perceptions of susceptibility, seriousness, benefits, and barriers influence women's health-seeking behaviours during pregnancy and childbirth. A review of recent empirical studies revealed that economic hardship, transportation difficulties, patriarchal norms, low female autonomy, and poor quality of care remain dominant challenges in rural Nigeria. Socio-cultural practices such as reliance on traditional birth attendants and herbal remedies, further limit timely access to skilled maternal care. Additionally, women's perceived disrespect and negative attitudes from health professionals discourage repeat visits to health facilities. The findings emphasize that gender inequality is a structural determinant of maternal health outcomes, sustaining high maternal mortality and poor well-being among rural women. The study concludes that achieving equitable maternal healthcare requires strengthening primary healthcare systems, improving women's empowerment, and enforcing inclusive health financing policies. It recommends that maternal health services be subsidized or made free, with mandatory health insurance coverage for vulnerable populations, investment in rural health infrastructure, and training programs that promote respectful maternity care. Such interventions will enhance access, reduce inequality, and align Nigeria with the Sustainable Development Goals on health and gender equity.

Keywords: Maternal, healthcare, women, antenatal, services

INTRODUCTION

Maternal care involves a range of measures designed to alleviate risk factors, manage health conditions, and ensure the welfare of both women and children. Maternal health (MH) services focus on preserving the well-being of women prior to and throughout pregnancy, during labor, and in the postpartum phase. Maternal health is fundamental for the well-being and productivity of populations (Miller & Belizan, 2015). Despite the World Health Organization's objective 3.1 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for 2030 to diminish the global maternal mortality ratio to below 70 per 100,000 live births (Global Health Observatory, 2023; United Nations, 2023), nearly 800 women continue to die daily due to complications arising from pregnancy and childbirth, translating to one fatality every two minutes (UNICEF, 2021). Unfortunately, the most of these mortality cases transpire in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), with over fifty percent of these fatalities occurring in Sub-Saharan Africa (UNICEF, 2021; WHO, 2023).

Maternal mortality (MM) constitutes a significant challenge in Nigeria. The 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) indicated a maternal mortality ratio of 512 per 100,000 live births (National Population Commission and ICF, 2019), with latest projections positioning Nigeria as the fourth highest internationally in maternal mortality ratio (UNICEF, 2023).

The WHO attributed the elevated incidence of maternal mortality in Nigeria to disparities in access to healthcare services. (World Health Organization, 2019). Evidence indicates that the majority of maternal fatalities might be averted if all pregnant women had access to affordable and direct interventions, together with care from qualified health professionals during pregnancy and childbirth (Bhutta et al., 2014; Kyei-Nimakoh et al., 2017; WHO 2023). An essential resolution to maternal mortality is a responsive healthcare system that delivers maternal health services across a continuum of care, incorporating high-quality antenatal care (Mothupi et al., 2018; Emiru et al., 2020). Antenatal care (ANC) refers to the medical attention administered by qualified healthcare professionals to pregnant women and adolescent girls, aimed at optimizing health outcomes for both the mother and the fetus throughout gestation (WHO, 2016).

The WHO (2016) guidelines now advocate for a minimum of eight antenatal care (≥ 8) visits to enhance maternal outcomes and ensure a more favorable experience for expectant women. The utilization of antenatal care (ANC) is regarded as a method to mitigate elevated maternal mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa (Mekonnen et al., 2019). Consistent and suitable attendance at ANC facilitates the prompt identification of pregnancy-related concerns and the implementation of necessary interventions to prevent potential consequences (Neogi et al., 2018; Ermais and Laloto, 2021). It also offers the opportunity for critical health functions, including health promotion, screening and diagnosis, and disease prevention (WHO, 2016). Notwithstanding the potential advantages of proper implementation of ANC, research indicates that the coverage and use of these services remain insufficient in Nigeria (Fagbamigbe et al., 2021). The utilization of antenatal care in Nigeria appears to be linked to many sociodemographic and economic characteristics (Fagbamigbe and Idemudia, 2017; Adewuyi et al., 2018), and addressing these factors is suggested to enhance both uptake and appropriate use of ANC services. Despite the pertinent evidence indicating that access to professional pregnancy care can reduce maternal mortality, it remains insufficient to achieve a significant decrease in maternal fatalities in Nigeria (Ope, 2020). Existing studies are frequently focused on only one or two research regions within the country, and hence are not generalizable. There is an absence of systematic evidence regarding the predictive factors and obstacles to the utilization of antenatal care in Nigeria. This study aimed to address the research gap by analyzing prior studies on gender inequality and access to maternal healthcare services in Nigeria, offering an overview of predictive factors and perceived obstacles to the effective utilization of maternal healthcare services, including antenatal care.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the situation of gender inequality and access to maternal healthcare service in Nigeria: Implications for women's health. Specifically, the study looked at:

1. The state of maternal healthcare in Nigeria, particularly across rural areas
2. How does social exclusion and gender inequality shape maternal health outcomes in Nigeria.

Significance of the study

Gender inequality in Nigeria has remained a major challenge and its effects on healthcare service delivery and access by women has remained fatal with many women dying from poor healthcare access and maternal services. The study is therefore significant, as it showcases the prevailing factors affecting maternal healthcare services in Nigeria, the effects of the poor healthcare access on maternal health as well as the practical relevance which promotes knowledge on the relevant policies needed to address the challenges of poor healthcare access and maternal health outcomes in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework: Health Belief Model (HBM)

The health belief model, put forth by Rosenstock (1966), which is cited in Cockerham (1978), is a key psychosocial model of health seeking behavior (activity taken by a person who believes themselves healthy for the purpose of preventing disease) or illness behavior (activity undertaken by a person who feels ill for the purpose of gaining relief).

According to the National Cancer Institute (NCI), 2002, the health belief model is a hypothesis that is frequently utilized in health promotion and health education. Scientists employ the Health Belief Model (HBM) as a method to try and forecast health behaviors. By concentrating on a person's attitudes and beliefs, it is also a psychological model that is used to explain and predict a person's health behavior. Social psychologists working in the United States in the 1950s first established this idea, which was later modified in the 1980s. The model was created as a conceptual framework for understanding health behavior and potential explanations for reasons why advised health actions are not taken (Becker and Rosenstock, 1984). It is predicated on the idea that certain elements play a major role in a person's willingness to alter her health-related behaviors. Four perceptions; perceived seriousness, perceived susceptibility, perceived advantages, and perceived barriers, serve as the model's major constructs. Each of these views can be used alone or in combination to explain health-related behaviors, such as infertility-related health problems. The health belief model has recently been broadened to incorporate cues to action, motivating factors, and self-efficacy as a result of the addition of additional elements.

Depending on how important a person perceives a consequence to be, there is a chance that they will alter their health-related behaviors in order to prevent it. **Perceived seriousness:** The concept of perceived seriousness refers to a person's perception of the severity or significance of a condition.

Perceived Susceptibility: Refers to personal risk or sensitivity, which is one of the more potent beliefs that influence people to engage in healthier behavior. Unless they feel at risk, people will not alter their health-related activities. The likelihood of participating in behavior to reduce the risk increases with perceived risk.

Perceived Benefits: A person's perception of the value or utility of a new behavior in lowering the chance of contracting a disease is the basis for the construct of perceived benefit prefers to adopt healthier habits when they think doing so will lower their risk of contracting a disease. If there is nothing in it for them, such as having an infertile lady eventually give birth to a child, convincing people to change their behavior might be challenging.

Perceived obstacles: One of the main reasons people do not alter their health-related behaviors is that they believe doing so will be challenging. Sometimes there are social difficulties as well as physical difficulties. It can be expensive in terms of time, money, and effort to change one's health habits. This component of the health belief model addresses the problem of the barrier to change because most people find it difficult to make changes. This is a personal assessment of the barrier to changing behavior. A person must believe that the advantages of the new behavior exceed the drawbacks of maintaining the old behavior in order for it to be accepted. This makes it possible to go beyond obstacles and adopt the behavior.

Review of relevant literature

The utilization of maternal health care services is a critical health concern that impacts both maternal and child survival, as it reduces maternal mortality and morbidity while enhancing the well-being of women and their children during the prenatal, perinatal, and postnatal periods. Maternal healthcare consumption is influenced by numerous global factors. Identified factors include the availability, quality, and cost of services; health beliefs and personal characteristics of users; maternal education; paternal employment; maternal age; maternal autonomy; number of previous pregnancies; and access to health facilities (ZelalemAyele et al., 2014). Additionally, several socio-demographic characteristics were discovered as influencing a mother's decision to utilize maternal healthcare services. Mallick et al. (2016) identified a significant correlation between a mother's childhood home, household socioeconomic position, maternal age at birth, parity, urban-rural locale, and region/geopolitical zone and the utilization of maternal health care facilities in households.

The use of maternal health care services in Nigeria is beset by challenges, especially in rural regions. Poverty, inadequate education, deficient infrastructure, governmental corruption and negligence, cultural attitudes, and insufficient awareness of the need of maternal health care have been previously highlighted (Obiyan & Kumar, 2015). In Nigeria's geopolitical zones, women in the southern area were more inclined to employ maternal health care services than their counterparts in the northern region (FMoH Nigeria, 2018). Residing in rural regions of developing nations, such as Nigeria, entails living in underprivileged

communities for social amenities and infrastructure (Mezmur et al., 2017). The socioeconomic difference in the use of maternal healthcare services in Nigeria has increased throughout the years (Okoli et al., 2020). The global well-being of mothers is a multifaceted topic influenced by various factors, including socioeconomic position, healthcare access, and cultural standards. Mothers in low and middle-income nations are more prone to adverse health and well-being (Mariani et al., 2017). This results from numerous factors, including restricted access to healthcare, insufficient nutrition, and elevated poverty levels. A significant number of mothers in low and middle-income nations lack access to essential healthcare services, including prenatal care, childbirth, and postnatal care (Dahab & Sakellariou, 2020). This indicates an increased likelihood of difficulties during pregnancy and labor, as well as a diminished probability of receiving necessary postnatal treatment (Olonade et al., 2019). Investigated the implications of maternal mortality and maternal healthcare in Nigeria, concluding that, in addition to medical-related causes (both direct and indirect), many socio-cultural and socioeconomic factors affect pregnancy outcomes. Unfortunately, an inadequate healthcare system, resulting from fragile social structures, contributes to maternal mortality, which has detrimental repercussions on the socioeconomic growth of any nation (Olonade et al., 2019).

Consequently, it is essential for the government to eliminate poverty to guarantee sustainable development. Poverty constitutes a significant obstacle to obtaining healthcare and other resources that can enhance maternal well-being (Dahab & Sakellariou, 2020). Women are more prone to poverty than men due to reduced participation in paid employment, lower educational attainment, and diminished property ownership. Underprivileged moms are more prone to encounter problems during pregnancy and childbirth, and they are less likely to afford the necessary treatment for recovery. Poverty significantly contributes to maternal mortality by hindering women's access to sufficient and adequate medical care, as they cannot afford quality antenatal services. Simultaneously, the Sustainable Development Goals represent a resolute pledge to complete the initiated efforts and eradicate poverty in all its manifestations by 2030. Moreover, pregnancy is a condition of significant physiological nerve strain that necessitates heightened nutritional requirements. Proper and high-quality maternal nutrition is essential for women's health and reproductive efficacy, as well as for the health, survival, and development of children (Bloomfield et al., 2013). Regrettably, numerous moms in poor and middle-income nations lack access to a healthful food (Kavle and Landry, 2018). This may result in anemia, malnutrition, and further health complications that might exacerbate the risks associated with pregnancy and childbirth.

Barriers to maternal healthcare access in Nigeria

Economic Factors

Research indicates that both direct and indirect expenses of prenatal care services often impede access to maternal healthcare in Nigeria. Certain research indicated that the payment method for antenatal care (ANC) affected both utilization and the attainment of the WHO-recommended number of ANC visits (Elkhatib et al., 2020; Sui et al., 2021). These studies indicated that moms with health insurance or access to free maternal care were more inclined to complete ≥ 8 antenatal care appointments. This aligns with other research from Nigeria and Ghana (Blanchet et al., 2012; Ahuru et al., 2021). The above 95% usage of antenatal care (ANC) among expectant and nursing women in some rural and semi-urban communities in Ondo State, southwestern Nigeria, in 2007 was ascribed to the provision of complimentary ANC services in the region (Akanbiemu et al., 2013).

Transportation

Transportation-related obstacles, including expenses and distance to healthcare facilities, are frequently cited as significant impediments to the utilization of antenatal care services in numerous studies. Research indicated that women residing near healthcare facilities or who viewed the nearest health facility as accessible had increased levels of antenatal care consumption (Ademuyiwa et al., 2020; Idowu et al., 2022). Poor road access, particularly in rural areas, may deter pregnant women from seeking antenatal care services (Ahuru et al., 2020; Owigho & Isara, 2022). Research indicates that women are more likely to access antenatal care services when these services are seen to be conveniently located near their residences (Adedokun and Yaya, 2020; Hassen et al., 2021).

Socio-cultural Practices and Beliefs

Culture influences women's perceptions on antenatal care. Owigho and Isara (2022) observed that pregnant women who partake in cultural practices, such as herbal remedies and abdominal massage, are more likely to deliver with traditional birth attendants, despite having attended antenatal care at a healthcare institution. The patriarchal society in Nigeria significantly hinders women's autonomy in health decision-making (Okunola, 2022). The accessibility of maternal healthcare treatments for women is significantly influenced by the social support of their spouses and the endorsement of their families. It is imperative to eliminate all manifestations of inhumane discrimination and gender inequality, thereby empowering women to make decisions regarding their health requirements (United Nations, 2023). A lack of awareness of ANC was identified as an impediment to its utilization (Eke et al., 2021; Owigho & Isara, 2022), highlighting the necessity for community-driven health promotion initiatives.

Standard of care

Women who viewed or believed they received substandard care were less inclined to seek antenatal care services. (Okonufua et al., 2018; Ahuru, 2020; Idowu et al., 2022). The research conducted by Eke et al. (2021) revealed that participants reported infrequent presence of healthcare staff, and when they do appear, their demeanor dissuades women from returning. The negative demeanor of healthcare professionals prompts women to seek services from traditional birth attendants.

CONCLUSION

Global initiatives are unwavering in their pursuit of achieving equitable access to maternal healthcare by 2030, in accordance with the global objectives for women's and children's health and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This systematic review enhances the existing knowledge about predictive factors and obstacles to antenatal care usage in Nigeria. The findings from this review are essential to Sustainable Development Goals 3, 5, and 10, which aim to enhance global health and well-being, empower women and affirm their autonomy and societal roles, and mitigate inequality in access to healthcare services regardless of gender and socio-economic status. Efficient collaboration among governmental and non-governmental organizations, along with global communities, must guarantee the integration of policies aimed at enhancing the accessibility, affordability, and quality of ANC services and UHC within the health system, positioning Nigeria to meet the SDG targets for 2030. Future research could investigate the obstacles to antenatal care utilization from the providers' viewpoints in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings from the examined literature, the study proposes the following recommendations: Maternal healthcare services in Nigeria should be provided at no cost or subsidized, as evidenced by their good effect on the utilization of antenatal care in several African nations. Health insurance ought to be mandated, encompassing a comprehensive benefits package, particularly for the impoverished, vulnerable, and informal sectors of the people in the country.

It is strongly recommended to allocate sufficient budget to maternal healthcare, equip healthcare units and facilities with appropriate medical supplies, enhance capacity and training for healthcare workers, improve infrastructure, and ensure comprehensive geographical coverage of healthcare services, particularly in rural areas.

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